

Light-induced Oxidation of Secondary Alcohols in the Presence of Benzoyl Peroxide and *N*-Bromosuccinimide

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Light-induced oxidation of secondary alcohols (benzhydrol, acenaphthenol, 1-phenylethanol and 1-(4-phenyl)-phenylethanol) at room temperature in the presence of benzoyl peroxide and *N*-bromosuccinimide in dichloromethane afforded ketones and other by-products.

Balsells and Frasca¹ reported the photolysis of secondary aromatic alcohols leading to the formation of complex mixture and the carbonyl products in low yield (<13 %) alongwith ethers. In continuation of our quest for light-induced reactions^{2,3}, light-accelerated oxidation of secondary alcohols in presence of benzoyl peroxide and *N*-bromosuccinimide has been reported here.

Results and Discussion

The secondary alcohols were kept in diffused sun-light in the presence of benzoyl peroxide and it was observed that the reaction in diffused sun-light for 3 h gave negative results in all the cases. However, when benzhydrol (1)⁴ was irradiated in pyrex reactor (3 130 and 3 660 Å)⁵ in the presence of benzoyl peroxide in dichloromethane for 3 h, 1,1,1',1'-tetraphenyldimethylether (2) was obtained (Table 1) whose structure was established by means of nmr spectrum consisting of two singlets at δ 7.35 and 5.40 in the integration ratio of 10 : 1, thereby confirming its structure. In addition to this ether, benzophenone (3), alongwith one unidentified product was also obtained. Benzoic acid emanating from benzoyl peroxide was also obtained.

1-Acenaphthenol (4)⁶ on being irradiated in the presence of benzoyl peroxide in dichloromethane for 3 h gave 1-acenaphthenone (5) alongwith some tarry product. The structure of 1-acenaphthenone

was confirmed by its nmr spectrum : δ 8.05 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 2.5 Hz, H-8), 7.94 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 2.5 Hz, H-6), 7.75 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 2.5 Hz, H-5), 7.72 (1H, t, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-7), 7.52 (1H, t, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-4); 7.40 (1H, dd, *J* 9.0, 2.5 Hz, H-3) and 3.82 (2H, s, C₂ protons).

However, 1-phenylethanol (6)⁷ when irradiated in the presence of benzoyl peroxide for 3 h in dichloromethane gave an unidentified product alongwith 1,1'-dimethyl-1,1'-diphenyldimethyl ether (7), 1-phenylethylbenzoate (8), acetophenone (9) and benzoic acid. Compound 7 was characterised as a mixture of two diastereomers as is evident from its nmr spectrum which consisted of two singlets in the ratio of 5 : 4 at δ 7.33 and 7.29 followed by quartets at δ 4.53 and 4.25 in the ratio of 4 : 5. The methyl protons of two isomers resonated at the two positions, i.e. δ 1.49 and 1.35 thereby confirming the structure. The structure of 1-phenylethylbenzoate (8) was confirmed by its nmr spectrum : δ 8.10 (2H, d, *J* 9.0 Hz, H-2 and H-6), 7.60–7.20 (8H, m, rest of ArH), 6.15 (1H, q, *J* 7.0 Hz, H-1 ethyl proton) and 1.65 (3H, d, *J* 7.0 Hz, CH₃ protons). 1-(4-Phenyl) phenylethanol (10)⁸ on irradiation in the presence of benzoyl peroxide for 3 h gave an unidentified semisolid alongwith *p*-phenylacetophenone (11), the starting alcohol (10), benzoyl peroxide and benzoic acid. The structure of 11 was confirmed by its

TABLE 1—PRODUCTS OBTAINED FROM THE PHOTOLYSIS OF SECONDARY ALCOHOLS IN PRESENCE OF BENZOYL PEROXIDE

Compd	Irrad time h	Yields (%)			
		Unreacted compound	Primary product	Secondary product	Unidentified product
Benzhydrol	3	—	Benzophenone (52)	(i) 1,1,1',1'-Tetraphenyl dimethyl-ether (40) (ii) Benzoic acid (85)	3
Acenaphthenol	3	—	Acenaphthenone (84)	Benzoic acid (86)	75
1-Phenylethanol	5	—	Acetophenone (72)	(i) 1,1'-Dimethyl-1,1'-diphenyl dimethyl-ether (11) (ii) 1-Phenylethylbenzoate (5) (iii) Benzoic acid (85)	6
1-(4-Phenyl)phenylethanol	3	11	<i>p</i> -Phenylacetophenone (74)	(i) Benzoic acid (70) (ii) Benzoylperoxide (10)	5

nmr spectrum : δ 8.0 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-6), 7.70 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3 and H-5), 7.50–7.20 (5H, m, rest of ArH) and 2.50 (3H, s, CH₃ protons).

Then the study of photolysis of secondary alcohols was thought worthwhile in the presence of *N*-bromosuccinimide. Benzhydrol (diphenylmethanol; **1**) was irradiated in dichloromethane in the presence of *N*-bromosuccinimide for 5 min and benzophenone (**3**) was obtained (Table 2). However, the dark reaction for 1 h did not show any conversion at all. 1-Acenaphthenol (**4**), when irradiated in dichloromethane in the presence of *N*-bromosuccinimide for 5 min, gave acenaphthenone (**5**). Its structure was confirmed by m.m.p. with the authentic sample and its nmr spectrum which was superimposable with that of the authentic sample. It was accompanied by an intractable mixture which could not be separated even on preparative tlc. One more product was also obtained, which could not be identified. However, 1-phenylethanol (**6**) gave instant reaction with *N*-bromosuccinimide and 30% yield of acetophenone was obtained in the dark only in 15 min, but

on irradiation photoacceleration was observed and irradiation for 5 min only, consumed whole of the 1-phenylethanol.

1-(4-Phenyl)phenylethanol (**10**) did not give any reaction in 15 min in diffused sun-light in the presence of *N*-bromosuccinimide in dichloromethane. However, on being irradiated with *N*-bromosuccinimide for 5 min it gave *p*-phenylacetophenone (**11**) whose structure was confirmed by its nmr spectrum which was superimposable over that of the authentic sample. *p*-Phenylphenacyl bromide (**12**) was also obtained whose structure was confirmed by its NMR and mass spectra : δ 8.10 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-2 and H-6), 7.68 (2H, d, J 9.0 Hz, H-3 and H-5), 7.85–7.05 (5H, m, rest of ArH) and 4.42 (2H, s, CH₂ protons). An unidentified product was also obtained alongwith tarry material.

Although secondary alcohols undergo photolysis on being irradiated in the absence of any catalyst and the product distribution is such that in most of the cases the yield of carbonyl product is very

TABLE 2—PRODUCTS OBTAINED FROM THE PHOTOLYSIS OF SECONDARY ALCOHOLS IN PRESENCE OF *N*-BROMOSUCCINIMIDE

Compd	Irrad time min	Yields (%)			
		Unreacted compound	Main product	Other product	Unidentified product
Benzhydrol	5	—	Benzophenone	—	—
1-Acenaphthenol	7	—	1-Acenaphthenone (69)	—	(I) 11 (II) 6
1-Phenylethanol	5	—	Acetophenone (89.5)	—	—
1-(4-Phenyl)- phenylethanol	5	—	<i>p</i> -Phenyl- acetophenone (42)	<i>p</i> -Phenylphenacyl bromide (43)	(I) 8 (II) 5

small except where the nitro group is present in position-4¹. The major products, however, were the ethers, diols and dioxanes whose formation may be attributed to the photolysis of resultant ketone in the course of long duration of irradiation. But the light-induced oxidation of secondary alcohols in the presence of benzoyl peroxide and *N*-bromosuccinimide, offers an excellent method for the oxidation of secondary alcohols (Scheme 1). Comparison of the products shows that the yield of ketones in our study is very high (> 72%) and the method can be used as a quick preparative method for the photolytic formation of ketones. Moreover, the dark reactions in presence of NBS and Bz₂O₂ did not show any reaction, whereas in a short period ~15 min of irradiation in presence of NBS and 3–5 h in the presence of Bz₂O₂, the yields of the carbonyl products are above 72%. This method can be used as a preparative photolytic method.

Besides the ketones other secondary products were isolated from the photolysate, namely, ethers and esters. In the case of 1-(4-phenyl)phenylethanol in the presence of *N*-bromosuccinimide, a side-chain substitution product, ω-bromoketone was also isolated. The formation of ether and ester may be explained by analogy with the work of Balsell and Frasca¹, whereas the formation of ω-bromoketone may have taken place through abstraction of a hydrogen from the methyl group, followed by its combination with Br radical (Scheme 2).

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. Nmr spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) and Jeol

Scheme 1

Scheme 2

FT-90 spectrometers and ir spectra on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer

Benzhydrol⁴, 1-acenaphthenol⁶, 1-phenylethanol⁷ and 1-(4-phenyl)phenylethanol⁸ were synthesised by the procedures reported earlier

General method of photolysis : A two-piece pyrex reactor equipped with a nitrogen gas bubbling leak, a condenser with a guard tube and 125 W high pressure mercury vapour lamp (Philips) in the inner probe, was placed in a water tank in which the flow of water was regulated to effect external cooling in order to maintain the reaction temperature (20–25°). The reactor was charged with secondary alcohol

(0.01 mol) in dichloromethane (100 ml) and benzoyl peroxide or *N*-bromosuccinimide (0.015 mol) and the lamp was switched on. The progress of the reaction was monitored by tlc. When a substantial change became discernible, the lamp was switched off and the contents were chilled (to quench the reaction mixture) in an ice-salt bath. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue was chromatographed over silica gel with solvents of increasing polarity using benzene and acetone mixtures as eluents. The products obtained in various fractions were further purified by recrystallisation.

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